

DIGITAL BASED VOLUNTEER RECRUITMENT

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ABSTRACT

The role of volunteers in NGO activities very important. Volunteers contribute their time, energy, and thoughts to activities led by NGOs. NGOs need media that can act as a link between the institute and volunteers. Digital media which functions as a marketplace is very helpful for NGOs in disseminating their programs and facilitating the recruitment of volunteers. Indorelawan is one of the social marketplaces in Indonesia that brings together institutions and potential volunteers. The purpose of this study was to determine the role of digital media in recruiting volunteers for social activities. This research uses the communication science theories that are including marketing communication theory and new media. The paradigm used in this research is the constructivist paradigm with a qualitative approach and a dialectical method based on a case study on the Indorelawan website. The data collection was conducting In-depth interviews with Marsya Nurmaranti as Director of Indorelawan. Conclusion: the use of a website that functions as a social marketplace is useful in the dissemination of NGO programs include volunteer recruitment. The utilization of the website can also support as a form of educating volunteers in carrying out social activities.

Keyword: digital, marketplace, recruitment, volunteer

INTRODUCTION

Digital media have a strategic role to play as the right communication media to collaborate to build the same perception among the parties that have an interest in the world of volunteers. This role should provide support for the advancement of social activities in society through skills development and open up opportunities for people who volunteer to engage in social activities. Volunteers are individuals who volunteer their time, energy, and personal funds to help others for social welfare. In Indonesian KBBI, a volunteer is called a volunteer. Volunteering is a person or group of people who help, with a commitment to help spontaneous individuals, families, communities to solve social problems without expecting benefits (Jedlicka, 1990).

Initially, the term volunteer was implementing various activities carried out by NGOs (non-governmental organizations). Non-profit NGO activities are highly dependent on volunteer services to mobilize their various social activities. In Indonesia, voluntary recruitment efforts have often encountered all kinds of obstacle types. Voluntary recruitment

restrictions include the fact that the volunteering profession is not popular in the community yet. Many people still don't understand the role of volunteering. Another obstacle experienced by NGOs is the lack of socialization media for voluntary recruitment. Social NGO activities certainly do not allow advertising and mass media that require a large budget. Another realization is the limited availability of media as a marketplace in the marketing of social activities in Indonesia.

One website functions as a marketplace in the marketing of social activities, including voluntary recruitment is Indorelawan. Indorelawan's mission is the collaboration between volunteers and organizations/communities for the social mission easier to do. Indorelawan has created a website called Marketplace Indorelawan.org. Indorelawan was a pioneer by people professionals from any background, namely Widharmika Agung (a graduate of Harvard Kennedy School), Zaky Prabowo (Haas Business School - UC Berkeley), Retha Dunga, (Australian National University), Ari Awan (technopreneur as the founder of several a start-ups in Japan) who are familiar with the world of volunteering while still studying. Indorelawan's goal is not only to provide information on volunteering opportunities but also to provide training on volunteer management and a forum for collaboration.

The use of website media as a marketplace for involuntary recruitment is cannot separate from the use of digital technology. Digital media make it easy for users to disseminate information without limiting time and space. The website also has advantages over other digital media with a wide reached not limited to friendship, and it also has effective branding.

This study describes how to digital-based volunteer recruitment. It is very important how the role of digital media in social sector during pandemic. This study aims to explain the digital-based volunteer recruitment. In Indonesia, a social marketplace is not popular. It is very interesting to explain digital based volunteer recruitment.

Indorelawan has several features on the website that facilitate communication between volunteers and organizations, as well as collaboration between organizations/communities, giving Indorelawan not only a place to find information but also a place to manage volunteers. The majority of volunteers who are members of Indorelawan are aged 18-24 (students and university students). To date, Indorelawan has 150,000 volunteers, and 2,600 social organizations/communities (as of July 2020) spread across Indonesia. This figure is dynamic, can be checked on the homepage (www.indorelawan.org).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Volunteer

Volunteering is a person or group of people who help, with a commitment to help spontaneous individuals, families, communities, solve social problems without expecting benefits (Jedlicka, 1990; Wilson, 2000; Henderson to Sergeant & Sedlacek, 1990). Activities with positive consequences for others, carried out by volunteers, with the ability to act authentically, well, correctly according to values, situations, and history of volunteering are called voluntary activities (Meier & Stutzer, 2004; Henderson in Sergeant & Sedlacek, 1990). Volunteering can contribute through energy, thoughts, talents, and including intellectual skills and assets to help others (volunteer activities). Volunteers spend more time and are organized in aid behavior, compared to the act of assisting foreigners in general, so the time spent

volunteering can be a predictor of volunteer activity (Nugroho, 2007; Snyder & Onoto in Taylor, Peplau, & Sears), 2009). The amount of time volunteers do character-based activities to help individuals, families, communities solve social problems with a sense of sincerity, and a spirit of devotion means the frequency of volunteer activities. (Natalya and Herdiyanto, 2016)

Point of view from the implementation pattern, three patterns of volunteering currently being developed. First, the activities were coordinating incidentally or continuously carried out. For example, social services activities and blood donations in the context of an institution or company anniversary. Third, volunteer activities that are managed by groups or organizations professionally and continuously. This third pattern is characterized by a strong commitment of volunteers (both written and oral) to be actively involved in the activities, the existence of daily routine and continue the activities, and the existence of divisions or organizations that recruit the special volunteers professionally and manage them as well. ¹

Digital Recruitment

Digital recruitment is a way of leveraging technology to source, assess, attract, select, and recruit candidates for open positions. It includes everything like career websites, leveraging job boards, recruiting through mobile, social hiring, and online assessments. (<https://content.wisestep.com/digital-recruitment/>)

Digital recruitment is the process of recruiting employees using electronic resources, particularly on the Internet (Zin, Fazlin, Nik, Mat, & Alias, 2016). The recruitment process has evolved to be no more traditional than making advertisements in newspapers, using television commercials, hiring agents, and so on. Since the mid-1990s, online recruitment has started to develop rapidly and is widely used today by recruiters and job seekers (RoyChowdury & Srimannarayana, 2013).

Online Marketplace

An online marketplace (or online e-commerce marketplace) is a type of e-commerce website where product or service information providing by multiple third parties. Online marketplaces are the primary type of multichannel e-commerce and can be a way to streamline the production process. Online marketplaces are the primary type of multichannel e-commerce and can be a way to abridge the production process.

In an online marketplace, consumer transactions have been processing by the marketplace operator and then delivered and fulfilled by the participating retailers or wholesalers. These types of websites allow users to register and sell single items to many items for a "post-selling" fee. In general, because marketplaces aggregate products from a wide array of providers, the selection is usually extensive, and availability is higher than in vendor-specific online retail stores. (Tozzi, 2008).

The term marketplace has been popular since 1995 when people used digital media to make transactions. Since 2014, online marketplaces have become abundant. Some online

marketplaces have a wide variety of general interest products that cater to almost all consumer needs, in the others are consumer specific and cater to a particular segment.

The first online marketplace was popular in 1995. In that year, Amazon and eBay became famous, and many people used them. In the same year, a bank in America named The Presidential Bank had launched its first online banking. In 1998, PayPal was launching a product that offers more convenience for online transactions.

In Asia, Jack Ma Alibaba launched in China in 1999. In Indonesia, we already have several well known local marketplaces like Tokopedia and Bukalapak. These two online marketplaces were so successful in Indonesia that they became 2 of 4 Unicorn start-ups in Indonesia.

In Indonesia, online marketplaces are not much use for social activities. The use of online marketplaces can provide benefits for NGOs in recruiting program socialization as well as program campaigns.

New Media

Technological developments have led to the growth of new media. The existence of new media in the presentation of information tends to trigger social change and influences determining the lifestyle of the people. These social changes are supported by urbanization, modernization, migration, enhanced labor force, enhanced stratification, and enhanced social mobility. (De Fleur: 2006).

New media has different electronic technological devices with various application users. This new electronic media includes various technological systems such as transmission systems (via cable or satellite), miniaturization systems, information storage, and retrieval systems, image presentation systems (with a flexible combination of text and graphics), and control systems (with the computer). (McQuail, 1987)

The main characteristics that distinguish the new media from the old media are decentralization (the acquisition and selection of news are no longer entirely in the hands of the communicator), high skill (delivery via cable or satellite overcomes communication barriers, caused by other broadcasters), mutual communication (communicators can choose, reply, exchange information and connect directly with other recipients), and flexibility (flexibility in form, content, and use). (Hamidati: 2011)

Social media like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Path, and YouTube are new media types in the Online Media category. These new types of media allow ordinary people to talk, participate, share and create networks online (Hamidati: 2011)

METHODOLOGY

According to Guba (1990, 17 in Denzine Norman K. and Yvonna S. Lincoln, 2009: 123), a Paradigm is a series of basic beliefs that guide action. Paradigm deals with first principles, or basic principles. Paradigm is also normative, showing the practitioner what to do without the need for long existential or epistemological considerations (Mulyana, 2003: 9). Paradigm is a pattern or model of how parts work (behavior in which there is a specific context or time dimension), according to Meleong (2004: 49).

The paradigm used in this research is the constructivist paradigm with a qualitative approach and a dialectical method based on a case study. Constructivist paradigm, which is a paradigm that is almost the antithesis of an understanding that places observation and objectivity in the discovery of reality or science.

The constructivism paradigm can be traced from Weber's thought, which characterizes that human behavior is fundamentally different from natural behavior. Humans act as agents in action to construct social reality. The way of construction is made to understand or give their behavior. Weber saw that individuals who have an influence on society but with some notes that individual social actions are associated with rationality. The social action meant by Weber is in the form of actions that are directed at other people. It can also be in the form of "thinking" actions, or subjective, claiming to occur due to the positive influence of a particular situation (Sani, 2007: 1).

According to Ardianto (2007: 161), the basic principle of constructivism is that a person's actions are determined by the construction of himself as well as by the construction of the external environment from his perspective. Thus this communication can be formulated which is determined by itself under the influence of the outside world. At this point, we can present Ron Herre's theory on the difference between person and self. A person is a self that is involved in the public sphere in which there are sociocultural attributes of the community, while the self is a self that is determined by its different thoughts and some sociocultural influences in its community.

METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative method with a case study approach. Yin into the book "Case Study" said that:

Case studies are as considered as one of the comprehensive explanations related to various aspects of a person, group, organization, program, or social situation that is as far as possible an explored, pursued, and researched. Case studies also have a bearing on detailed research on a person or a social unit within a given period (Yin: 2008).

The data collection technique used by researchers was through interviews with the director of Indorelawan, namely Marsya Nurmaranti, and also documentation researThis study uses triangulation techniques to check creadiability. Satori and Komariah (2011: 94) suggest that "triangulation is checking data from various sources in various ways, and at various times". Triangulation is done by comparing and checking the data and information that has been obtained with different tools and times.

Satori and Komariah (2011: 170-171) divide triangulation into three, namely: (1) source triangulation, (2) technical triangulation, and (3) time triangulation. Source triangulation is done by looking for data from various sources that are still related to one another. Technique triangulation is done by using a variety of techniques to reveal the data carried out to the data source. Meanwhile, time triangulation is done by collecting data at different times.

The triangulation used in this research is source triangulation and technique triangulation. Source triangulation is done by checking information / data obtained through interviews with informants. Then the data is asked of other informants who are still related to one another.

Transferability is done by presenting research reports that are easy to read and provide clear, complete, systematic, and reliable information. Dependability is done by examining the

entire research process. Confirmability is done by checking the results of the research with the research process so that the data obtained can be traced to the correctness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Indonesia, volunteering is not very popular and is always identical to NGO activities. Many problems can be solved by involving many volunteers. Broad and complex social problems require the participation of various institutions including the government or companies. Voluntary contributions are needed to abridge social activities as well. "We believe that a meaningful change for Indonesia can only be achieved if more people are involved in social activities," Marsha said. Marsya added that they are volunteering not with their money but with their energy. One of our biggest dreams is to see volunteering as a lifestyle. "Where volunteers are no longer an exclusive social activity but have become a habit of Indonesian society," Marsya said.

Indorelawan's goal is not only to provide information on volunteering opportunities but also to provide training on volunteer management and a forum for collaboration. Also, our priority goal is to establish volunteering as a lifestyle. Marsya quotes Bung Karno as said, "if Pancasila used as an essence, then it is a matter of cooperation." Indorelawan believes that one of the keys to overcoming the social problems in Indonesia is cooperation, namely volunteering.

In 2013, when Indorelawan has founded, they had a website. In that year, we mostly used e-newsletters and FB to attract organizations and volunteers to use this platform. In 2014, Website 1.0 has launched in April 2015, and Web 2.0 (the current website) as well. Using the website extends the target network further. E-Newsletter and FB.

Marsya explained that the use of digital media on the website that functions as a social marketplace had become a "matchmaking agency" between volunteers and social organizations/communities. Through the internet, we create many social organizations/communities that make it easier for us to find volunteers through our online platform (www.indorelawan.org). All free places to volunteer and registration as a volunteer is doing online. We support all social issues of education, environment, health, human rights, and animal protection. So, the activities on our website do not belong to Indorelawan, but we are the third party that bridges it.

Social organizations can find volunteers with any job description that it could be as simple as clearing trash along the CFD road or becoming a videographer for the organization's video campaign. Meanwhile, volunteers can decide for themselves which activities have occupied according to the availability of time/location distances/topics of interest/skills. Volunteers choose they are appropriate for activities.

There are several features on the Indorelawan website that facilitate communication between volunteers and organizations, as well as collaboration between organizations/communities, making Indorelawan not only a place to find information but also a place to manage volunteers. Below is the Indorelawan.org Feature Table

INDORELAWAN.ORG FEATURE TABLE

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No	Type of Feature	Description	Goal
1	Find activity	This feature has used to find volunteer activities in various organizations	Prospective volunteers can find volunteer activities that match their interests at the right institution
2	Find organization	Find an organization that needs volunteers	volunteers can find the right institution to volunteer according to their interests
3	Looking for Volunteer	This feature has used as an organization to look for volunteer	Institutions can find volunteer candidates according to the required criteria
4	Way of work	The feature has consisted of a volunteer guide and an organization guide	Institutions and volunteers know the information they need

Source: processed by researchers

Through the Indorelawan.org website, people know that anyone can volunteer! "Our principle is that everyone can volunteer. Do you want to take a selfie while volunteering? Can! Do you want to find a mate if you volunteer? Yes! No reason to wait established, wait a lot of free time or wait for a snow-white heart to volunteer " The important thing is to work and engage in the activities you have chosen," Marsha explained.

The Indorelawan.org website has a feature that explains how to volunteer. This character explains about enrollment, the steps of which must be a profile that consists of complete biodata, followed by a search for activities, a list of activities, and an inspiration. The process of recruiting to become a volunteer usually takes a long time and depends on the needs of the organization in need. The recruitment process associated with certainty expertise usually has requirements that volunteers have to meet, including flexibility and time, and energy, for example, The need for the research or graphic design staff. On the other hand, volunteer needs related to online campaigns do not require binding time. As during the COVID pandemic, digital campaigns are in high demand by young people.

Based on the statement above, it is precisely clear that the Indorelawan.org website has the role of the wide to play as a marketplace that brings the institute and volunteers together. These can be saw based on access on 90/27/2020, and there were 2,882 institutions involved and 168,922 volunteers with 5,788 activities. On the Indorelawan website, features can be a view from different dimensions, namely the dimensions of the content, the usability, and the additions. The content dimension is dividing into 3 (three) criteria, namely the availability of information, the wide of information, and the presentation of information. The term content, in the context of recruitment, refers to the chosen configuration of information conveyed through the recruitment medium. The quantity, focus, and framing of the content have a direct effect on the attractiveness of job search organizations (Cober, Brown, Levy, Cober, & Keeping, 2003).

CONCLUSION

Voluntary recruitment activities and social activities are precisely important. Volunteers play a similarly important role in driving the event of social institutions. The need to recruit volunteers is made simple with the use of digital media. The Indorelawan.org website has served as a marketplace for bringing social institutions together with volunteers. The features of Indorelawan.org cover the dimensions of the content, benefits, and additional information.

SUGGESTION

Indorelawan.org needs to expand its socialization activities so that the name Indorelawan is better known and can be used by many people as a marketplace. Indorelawan can also collaborate with institutions or institutions that need volunteers in their social activities. A digital feature should be extra with the "Story of Volunteer" column that tells stories of success and inspiration to volunteer. This character is very beneficial for motivating yourself to volunteer.

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